

The CO₂-Solutions Living Lab: Advancing Carbon Farming and Nature-Based Solutions for Climate Resilience

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The CO₂-Solutions Living Lab is an agricultural Living Lab dedicated to advancing the first EU-wide voluntary framework for certifying high-quality carbon removals. It focuses on nature-based solutions that enhance carbon farming practices within regenerative agricultural systems. This initiative supports the Soil Mission by conserving and increasing soil organic stocks, reducing soil pollution, and enhancing soil biodiversity. Hosted by the Interbalkan Environmental Center (I-BEC) and a member of the European Network of Living Labs (ENOLL) since 2023, the CO₂-Solutions Living Lab emphasizes:

- Enhancing carbon sequestration and soil health through Nature-Based solutions.
- Promoting innovative carbon farming practices and technologies.
- Reducing agriculture's carbon footprint.
- Supporting climate-smart and nature-based solutions.

By integrating sustainable practices into agriculture, our Living Lab contributes to climate change mitigation, fostering both environmental and community resilience. Operating under the Quadruple Helix (QH) model, our Living Lab engages diverse stakeholders:

- Business stakeholders, including certification bodies, consultants, agri-tech companies, and environmental NGOs.
- Farmers, landowners, and cooperatives, directly involved in pilot projects.
- Academic institutions and research organizations, contributing expertise and driving innovation.
- Regional authorities and municipalities, ensuring policy alignment and implementation.

Key activities include supporting the carbon farming certification process, implementing nature-based solutions, conducting research, developing MRV tools, and fostering stakeholder collaboration. Regular workshops, webinars, and training sessions are organized for capacity building, reinforcing the initiative's value proposition. Additionally, the CO₂-Solutions Living Lab aligns with key policies such as the Climate Law, Nature Restoration Law, and Biodiversity Law.

We implement carbon farming solutions across five pilots with different crop types and over 10 demonstration sites in diverse pedoclimatic zones. These sites are pivotal for testing and evaluating practices, assessing their impact on soil health, carbon sequestration, and biodiversity. They also serve as educational hubs, hosting on-farm events to disseminate knowledge and practical solutions. This emphasis on real-life engagement ensures that solutions are practical, effective, and tailored to the specific needs of farmers and landowners. This involves interviews, surveys, pilot projects, field demonstrations, trainings, and workshops throughout all phases of the innovation cycle. This inclusive approach fosters ownership and ultimately maximizes the impact of the initiative.

The CO₂-Solutions Living Lab is making a substantial impact by sharing valuable information and innovations through various channels and fostering connections among diverse stakeholders to drive meaningful environmental change. Its mission to expand reach and impact is achieved by standardizing practices using tools like the Field Diagnostic Toolbox (FDT) and MRV protocols, fostering cross-sector collaboration through networking events, local community engagement, and research projects, expanding geographically with new demonstration sites, and

replicating effective tools and carbon sequestration methods. A key goal is to establish lighthouses of innovation—exemplary pilot sites that inspire replication across regions and sectors, amplifying the initiative’s positive environmental and social effects. Ultimately, our Living Lab is committed to educating communities, equipping them with the knowledge to adapt to climate change and implement preventative measures for a more climate resilient future.

Keywords: Carbon Farming, Climate Resilience, Soil Health, Nature-Based Solutions

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